

ANALGESIC ACTIVITIES OF THE AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. JUSS
STEM BARK IN ALBINO RATS

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ABSTRACT

The study on the analgesic activities of aqueous extract of *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark in albino rats was carried out. Rats were administered doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg intraperitoneally of the aqueous extract of *Ekebergia senegalensis* stem bark and a standard drug (pentazocine 10 mg/kg), and were subjected to hot plate and tail immersion tests maintained at a constant temperature of $50^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Latency to response was taken at 0, 15, 30, 60 and 90 mins after extract administration. The extract dose dependently produced significantly ($p<0.05$) analgesic activities in rats, in the both methods tested. The response was comparable to that of pentazocine in the hot plate method but higher than pentazocine in the tail immersion method. It was concluded that aqueous extract of *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark have analgesic activity in albino rats.

KEY WORDS: *Ekebergia senegalensis*, aqueous extract, analgesia, rats.

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INTRODUCTION

The conventional analgesics have some limitations as the opioids analgesics are associated with respiratory depression, constipation and dependence as side effect while the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) may cause gastrointestinal and renal damage. On the other hand, the medicinal plants have fewer side effects, cheap, accessible and culturally more acceptable (Parekh *et al.*, 2005). *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss (family; Maliaceae) is a medicinal plant that grows up to 30ft and it is distributed from Senegal to Angola but can also be found in southern and northern parts of Nigeria (Ndukwe, 2006). It is called rock mahogany and Madacin dutse in English and Hausa languages, respectively. The bark, root and leaf decoctions, infusions and maceration of the plant have been used in disease conditions such as gastritis, heart burn, dysentery, epilepsy, gonorrhoea, ulcer, boils, scabies, acne, pimples, abdominal pain, headache, helminthosis, fever, painful menstruation, and cough (Palmer *et al.*, 1972; Mbuya *et al.*, 1994; Egale *et al.*, 2006 and Bekele-Tesemma, 2007). It is also used to facilitate parturition (Grace *et al.*, 2002) and as an analgesic after hard labour to relief fatigue. While the plant is claimed to have analgesic effects, there is paucity of information on its scientific basis for this purpose. The objective of the study is to investigate the analgesic activity of the aqueous extracts of *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark in albino rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection and extraction

The stem bark of mature *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss was collected in Hong local government area of Adamawa state and was identified and authenticated by a plant taxonomist at the Department of Biological Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria. The bark of the plant was dried in the laboratory, pounded to a fine powder using pestle and mortar and then stored in a dry cylinder. The powdered stem bark weighing 200g was mixed with 1 litre of distilled water in 5litre capacity beaker and allowed to stand for 30mins at 65°C . It was then allowed to cool and then was shaken vigorously before filtration using Whatmann No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated in a rotary evaporator and stored at 4°C . The yield was 12.2g that is 6.1% (w/w).

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Experimental animals

Forty albino rats weighing between 115g and 260g of both sexes were obtained from the Veterinary Histology Laboratory, in the Department of Veterinary Anatomy, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Maiduguri. They were kept in clean plastic rat cages and allowed to acclimatise to the laboratory environment for a period of one week before the commencement of the experiments. They were fed with growers mash (Vital feeds, Jos, Nigeria Ltd) and water was provided *ad libitum*.

Evaluation of analgesic activity using hot plate test

Twenty adult rats of both sexes weighing between 115 and 243g were randomly divided into four groups of five rats each (A, B, C and D) and the method described by Sandabe *et al.* (2004) was used. They were deprived of food for 24hours before the commencement of the experiment. Those in group A received distilled water 0.5ml (negative control), those in group B received pentazocine (10mg/kg BW) served as the positive control while those in group C and D received the extract at 100 and 200mg/kg BW respectively. All treatments were by intraperitoneal routes. They were kept on Eddy's hot plate at a constant temperature of $50^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 0min, 15min and 30min. The time taken for either pad licking or jumping after the placement was recorded.

Evaluation of analgesic activity using tail immersion test

The test was performed as described previously by Turner (1965) and Akindele and Adeyemi (2006). The rats were screened and only rats that responded within 2 – 8 seconds by withdrawing their tail from water bath ($50^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) were selected. Twenty adult rats of both sexes weighing between 130 and 260g were randomly divided into four groups of five rats each. Their tails were marked at 5cm length from the caudal end using plasticine and deprived of food for 24hours before the experiments. Treatment was given as in the hot plate above. Tail immersion test was performed by dipping their tails (up to 5cm) in a water bath maintained at $50^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The reaction time was taken as the time (in seconds) when the rats withdraw their tails completely from the hot water. Readings were taken at 0, 15, 30, 60 and 90 mins after administration.

Statistical analysis

All data generated from the study were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation and analyzed statistically by two way analysis of variance - (ANOVA). Graphpad InStat® for window USA® computer software® was used for the analysis and $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

Table 1 present the effect of the aqueous extract of *E. senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark on hot plate test in rats. There were significant ($P < 0.05$) increases in time for either pad licking or jumping after the placement of the treated rats at the dosages of 100mg/kg BW (at 30mins) and 200mg/kg (at 15 and 30mins) of the extract. At the dosage of 200mg/kg BW the latency period increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) from 21.4 ± 6.3 at pre-treatment to 48.2 ± 11.1 and 59.4 ± 22.7 at 15 and 30mins respectively post treatment. Also when compared with the control (distilled water) there were significant ($P < 0.05$) increases in time for pad licking or jumping at the dosages of the extract 100mg/kg BW (at 30mins) and 200mg/kg (at 15mins and 30mins). At 30mins the effects were similar to that of the standard agent (pentazocine).

The result of analgesic effect of the extract on tail immersion test response in rats for duration of one and half hours as presented in Table 2, showed that there was no significance ($P > 0.05$) changes in the time for tail withdrawal at all dosages of extract administered except at 100mg/kg BW (at 30 mins and 90 mins) and 200mg/kg BW (at 90 mins) where the time for tail withdrawal were significantly ($P < 0.05$) shorter than that of the pre-treatment. Also when compared with the control (distilled water), there were no significant ($P > 0.05$) changes in time for the tail withdrawal at all dosages of the extract except at 200mg/kg BW (at 30mins and 60mins) where the time for tail withdrawal was significantly ($P < 0.05$) longer than that of the control. The standard agent (pentazocine) also produced significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in time withdrawal at 90 mins post administration when compared with that of the control. The effect of the extract at 200mg/kg BW was greater than that of pentazocine at 30 and 60 mins post administration.

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Table 1: Effect of aqueous extract of *E. senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark on hot plate response in Albino rats

Dosage/Dose	Reaction time (Min) Mean±SD		
	pretreatment	15min	30min
Control (Distil water 0.5ml)	31.6±4.4	25.2±5.5	22.2±6.6
Pentazocine 10mg/kg	33.0±6.7	60.4±6.2 ^{a,b}	64.8±8.6 ^{a,b}
Extract 100mg/kg	30.8±10.0	38.0±5.8	57.8±11.4 ^{a,b}
Extract 200mg/kg	21.4±6.3	48.2±11.1 ^{a,b}	59.4±22.7 ^{a,b}

^a = Significant (P<0.05) increase compared to the mean of pretreatment along the same row

^b = Significant (P<0.05) increase, compared to the mean of the control along the same column

n = 5

Table 2: Effect of aqueous extract of *E. senegalensis* A. Juss stem bark on tail immersion response in rats.

Dosage/Dose	Reaction time (Min) Mean±SD			
	pretreatment	15min	30min	60min
90min				
Control (0.5ml)	8.6±3.8	8.8±1.3 ^a	7.0±0.7 ^a	7.4±1.5 ^a
Pentazocine 10mg/kg	12.8±2.9	14.0±1.0	12.2±1.3	11.6±3.6
Extract 100mg/kg	17.2±4.3	20.0±4.7	10.0±3.2 ^a	2.2±3.1
Extract 200mg/kg	14.6±1.1	12.0±1.6	16.0±4.7 ^b	15.6±3.6 ^b

^a = Significant (P<0.05) decreased compared to the mean of pretreatment along the same row

^b = Significant (P<0.05) increase, compared to the mean of the control along the same column

n = 5

DISCUSSION

The analgesic or antinociceptive activity of aqueous extract of *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss. stem bark was evaluated using hot plate test and tail immersion methods in albino rats. The use of different models is significant in the detection of antinociceptive properties in a substance considering that using a variety of stimuli can recognise different types of pain and reveal the actual nature of antinociceptive test drugs (Bergerot *et al.*, 2006). The hot plate test is a central antinociceptive model in which opioid agents exert their analgesic effects via supraspinal and spinal receptors. Comparing reaction times obtained for animals treated with *E. senegalensis* extracts and the control values, it was apparent that the *E. senegalensis* extracts caused a considerable prolongation of latency times, which is indicative of centrally mediated activity.

Another evidence of a possible central effect of *E. senegalensis* extract was detected through the tail – flick test. This task is sensitive in assessing the effectiveness of centrally acting analgesic (Talhouk *et al.*, 2007). The tail immersion method is used to assess analgesic activity mediated mainly at the spinal level of the central nervous system (Wong *et al.*, 1994). The extract was effective in delaying tail withdrawal response. It produced significant (P<0.05) tail withdrawal effect at the 100mg/kg BW dosage tested 30min and 90mins post administration and at the 200mg/kg BW dosage tested, 30, 60 and 90mins post administration as compared with the control (distilled water) and was more effective than pentazocine at this dosage. When compared with the pretreatment, there were significant (p<0.05) decreases in the latency of response in the tail immersion. This is possible probably because of the pre sensitization of the rats due repeated exposure in the water bath or because of increase ambient temperature since the experiment took more than 1.5hours.

The extract dosage dependently increased the latency response to hot plate stimulus because the effect was observed at 30mins post administration at 100mg/kg BW but at the dosage of 200mg/kg BW the effect was observed 15mins and 30mins post administration, just as that of pentazocine. In the tail immersion test the effect of extract at the dosage of 200mg/kg BW was more than that of pentazocine 30 and 60 mins post administration when compared to the control. The plant may contain some active principles that possess analgesic properties

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that could be better than pentazocine. Previous work on this plant has revealed the presence of some phytochemicals such as glycosides, saponins, tannins and alkaloids (Ndukwe *et al.*, 2006). Tannins, saponins and alkaloids are known to possess analgesic activities (Starec *et al.*, 1988; Yin *et al.*, 2003; Akkola *et al.*, 2007). The recommendation of this plant by traditional medicine practitioner in controlling painful conditions such as abdominal pain, fatigue, arthritis, painful menstruation, difficulty in child birth, headache, heart burn, itching, sinusitis could be justified based on the positive result obtained in this research. Detailed investigation is needed to determine the specific active principles responsible for the analgesic activity and the mechanism of action of aqueous extract of *Ekebergia senegalensis* A. Juss. stem bark in rats.

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